

When the toaster knows what you are up to: The effect of mentalisation on the uncanny valley effect

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The uncanny valley effect describes an eerie feeling experienced during the interaction with robots that possess a high but imperfect human resemblance. While this phenomenon is mostly researched in terms of visual aspects, current studies suggest a comparable effect through cognitive and emotional similarities. During our study, we researched whether the ability of mentalisation evokes such an effect by comparing the perception of two robots with differing capabilities to understand mental states ($N= 220$). The results fail to support our hypotheses' full extent but show a significantly creepier perception of robots with highly developed mentalisation capabilities. They also suggest an influence of declarable attitudes towards robots on the effect instead of often discussed deeply rooted mechanisms.

Keywords: artificial intelligence; computer interaction; human likeness; mentalisation; uncanny valley effect

The uncanny valley effect is relevant in practical fields like robotics, animation, and computer-human interaction, as it is disputed in research. Originally brought forth by roboticist Masahiro Mori in 1970, it describes an increasingly positive reaction to robots with developed anthropomorphic features, which turns into a negative uncanny feeling if a certain threshold of human-likeness is reached without the object being human (Mori, 1970, as cited in MacDorman & Kageki, 2012). The shown response is mainly referred to as a feeling of unease rather than fear or contempt. This theory, initially build on Mori's observations that mainly concerned his own robots, extended itself over time to all anthropomorphic objects and is currently discussed in this context. Puppets, mannequins, or stuffed animals can also cause this effect (Yamada et al., 2012).

An example could be a teddy bear with a realistic-looking human denture or a puppet with great facial detail but dull eyes. Furthermore, the effect appears to be linked to human attributes in general and not limited to visual aspects. Gray & Wegner's study (2012) has shown that a computer capable of feeling was perceived more negatively by participants than a normal device without this function. While true electronic emotions are a somewhat distant concept, the simulation of human attributes in human-computer interaction is already present. Common smart speakers, AI (artificial intelligence) chat programs, and other voice-controlled systems endeavour to emulate a personality that is tangible to its user. Alan Turing, a cryptologist and main contributor to the decryption of the enigma code, proposed in 1950 the concept of his imitation game, which became later known as the Turing test. This process consists of a human tester who communicates with two interlocutors via text chat, of which one is also human, and the other is an AI. If the tester is unable to identify the AI through questioning correctly, it is attributed to be intellectually indistinguishable from humans.

Some AIs already passed this test; further developments might go far beyond that. It is still in progress but a functional program with full verbal conversations without being detected as artificial, like the Duplex system presented by Google in 2018 (Leviathan & Matias, 2018). In this ongoing humanisation of technology, the question arises of how much human-likeness is accepted in machines and which aspects are affected. In this study, we investigated the perception of robots with the capability of mentalisation. Mentalisation is described as 'the ability to understand one's own and others' mental states, thereby comprehending one's own and others' intentions and affects' (American Psychology Association, 2020). It is similar in concept to empathy but requires the combination of general knowledge and situational information to create a predictive model for a mental state instead of just putting oneself in somebody's place. Both constructs are suggested to be strongly linked (Hooker et al., 2008). Mentalisation is an indispensable ability regarding social interaction, self-reflection, and general mental health. Therefore, it is often researched in a clinical context, where it stands as a core for different treatments (Brockman & Kirsch, 2010). It is sometimes argued to be comprehensible in animals (Kasperbauer, 2017) but represents a distinctly human trait in its highly evolved form. There is an argument that algorithms are already capable of performing similar feats by data analysis. Modern algorithms deployed to manage requests are mostly concerned with predicting user-specific behaviour and offering a corresponding course of action. Famous examples include the recommendation system from Netflix (Gomez-Uribe & Hunt, 2015). However, the profile created in the process can be used to infer mental states or motivations depending on its complexity. We, therefore, wanted to explore whether this ability, which is normally essential for a functional social exchange, would be met with a negative reaction when implemented into a robot.

While it is a common design rule to avoid this uncanny degree of human-likeness, the effect seems complicated to replicate in studies. The uncanny valley's shape and existence have been researched with different methods and theoretical assumptions. Some methods include the rating of a picture series showcasing a gradual visual morph between an anthropomorphic object and a human face (MacDorman, 2006) or the usage of pre-rated pictures (Palomäki et al., 2018). The valley itself has been questioned to either be an uncanny cliff (Bartneck et al., 2007), invert itself in certain situations (Cheetham et al., 2014), or not exist at all (Bartneck et al., 2009). It could, in some cases, only be recreated if the unnatural movement were involved (Saygin et al., 2011), a mismatch between visual and auditive factors occurred (Mitchell et al., 2011), or deformities reminiscent of illnesses were formed during the morphing process (Seyama & Nagayama, 2007).

Furthermore, the concept of uncanny, as seen in different studies, lacks a uniform definition. While our study was not aimed at verifying the valley's shape through gradual comparison, we derived our assumption in favour of Moris' s original proposal. A robot with highly human-like attributes would be perceived more negatively by people than a robot without anthropomorphic features. As a measurement for 'uncanny', we adopted the procedure used in a meta-study by Palomäki et al. (2018), which split 'uncanny' in and individually researched nine different attributes. Our main hypotheses were: (1) Robots with the ascribed ability of mentalisation will be rated significantly lower in positive attributes than robots lacking this ability; (2) Robots with the ascribed ability of mentalisation will be rated significantly higher in negative attributes than robots lacking this ability. To further research if a difference in rating connected to the perceived human-likeness, we created the third hypothesis: (3) Robots with the ascribed ability of mentalisation will be rated

significantly more human-like than robots lacking this ability. The effect underlying the uncanny valley can overall be described as deeply rooted in the human psyche. Evolutionary and cognitive psychology brought forth different explanations for the phenomenon. A shown deviation from the human appearance could be interpreted as sickness and be instinctively avoided (Moosa & Ud-Dean 2010) or remind us of our mortality by blurring the line between living human and dead object (MacDorman, 2005). The blurring itself could also cause the effect because the image cannot be categorised, resulting in unease (Yamada et al., 2012). It may also be a combination of these effects that causes a certain degree of human-likeness to be unsettling. Nevertheless, this effect is not the only contributor to the rating of a robot. Intelligent robots may not be a central part of everyday life but present a popular topic for film and fiction. Films like the *Terminator Series*, *Big Hero 6*, or the Stanley Kubrick classic *2001: A Space Odyssey* reaches millions of people respectively and offers a strong opinion on human-like computers' desirability (Young & Carpenter, 2018). Technical development, in general, can often be met with scepticism or unwillingness to adapt, depending on personal factors and the product (Godoe & Johansen, 2012). A negative perception can occur merely due to the unfamiliarity and speculated danger potential of a robot. Furthermore, there is a philosophical component to the determination of human likeness.

Whether it is a wish to accept autonomous systems as 'alive and equal to humans' or the determination to isolate human attributes from objects strictly or other lifeforms, for that matter, the willingness to ascribe human likeness varies between people (Waytz et al., 2010). It is the difference between a dog whose main purpose consists of entertaining the children and a dog that is part of the family with an emotional life that has to be cared for. To accommodate these variables in the rating of human attributes in robots, we implemented the general attitude towards robots, the commitment to technology, and the individual anthropomorphism as covariates.

METHODS

Participants

Our sample was recruited through the website Survey Circle, which promotes reciprocal participation in studies for researchers and builds up an interest in these studies through different social media outlets. We implemented a listwise exclusion for datasets, which had less than four out of seven correct multiple-choice attention checks or were simply incomplete. From the originally planned nine attention checks, two were excluded due to the distribution of given answers matching random chance. We, therefore, interpreted them to be too difficult and not fit for distinguishing between conscientious and random answers. From 249 participants, 29 were excluded. Our final sample ($N = 220$) consisted of 142 females (age: mean = 25.65; $SD = 6.605$; range = 18–59), 0 divers and 68 male (age: mean = 28.46; $SD = 9$; range = 20–72) participants. We frequently checked for the number of usable datasets during the survey and ended it after achieving the sample size calculated with G*Power to be sufficient for the hypothesis. Our sample showed an above average educational distribution due to the Survey Circle's main userbase consisting of academics and was limited to German-speaking participants by the study's language.

Furthermore, the proportional dominance of psychological or sociological research on this site manifested itself in a corresponding gender distribution (Fowler et al., 2018). All participants were compensated with points that increased the leader-board rank of their study, which increased its attractiveness for other participants. They also had the chance to win one of three gift vouchers.

Materials

We conducted an online survey using a standard layout on the Sosci survey from 11th September 2020 to 5th January 2021 with a stated completion time of about 10 minutes. For the dependent variables, we implemented nine attributes concerning uncanniness, of which four were negative (disgusting, scary, repulsive, and creepy) and five were positive (pleasant, trustworthy, approachable, friendly, and nice) – (see Palomäki et al., 2018) – as well as two additional items measuring the extend of human-likeness. As possible covariates, we included the Negative Attitudes Towards Robots Scale (NARS) in its German version (Bartneck, 2019), Short Scale for Technology Commitment (originally called *Kurzskala zur Erfassung von Technikbereitschaft*), and the Individual Differences in Anthropomorphism Questionnaire (IDAQ). The NARS contains different statements on interactions with, societal changes through, and concerns about robots' evolution (Syrdal et al., 2009). Statements about technology commitment included the interest in new technology or the expected extent of self-control over the interaction with a product (Neyer et al., 2012). The IDAQ asks for the perceived extent to which different objects and animals could be considered to have free will, consciousness, intention, or emotion (Waytz et al., 2010).

Design

To explore a possible difference in the perception of robots due to the capability of mentalisation, participants were presented with and asked to rate two different robots. The survey started with a cover story inspired by a study from Bernotat & Eyssele (2018) declaring the surge of European interest in Japanese household robots and their market potential as our research intention. Following the introduction, participants were given a detailed description of a household robot, including general information about the production, product measurements, operation and cleaning capability, model-specific functions, and a photo of the robot Olivia from ASORO Social Robotics. Olivia was shown to be perceived as neither uncanny nor sympathetic by humans in a study by Rosenthal-van der Pütten (2014). We, therefore, chose it as a representation of the product to minimise a visual uncanny valley effect on the rating and described it to be only 140cm tall to limit its potential to be deemed a physical threat. The cover story described the robots as one of the two newest models from a production line focusing on exploring different ways of personalising interaction with customers. Its general function could be described as a combination of smart speaker and vacuum cleaner robot (only a frame of reference, not described this way in the study), capable of wet-and dry-cleaning different surfaces using an advanced visual navigation system and different interchangeable tools. Once adapted to its working environment, it could navigate freely and accept voice commands or inputs on a touchpad embedded in its front. It was described to have a good general understanding of verbal commands and corresponding functions comparable to other modern intelligent speakers.

This general information, as well as the attached photo of Olivia, were identical in both descriptions. Robot A with the name extension Mod and Robot B labelled Dynamic differed only in developing and implementing behavioural patterns independent on their user. While Robot Mod could be moved with different predefined patterns, Robot Dynamic developed its own by creating a statistical model of its user to change the behaviour according to their predicted needs, wants, and moods. General and model-specific information were visually separated in both descriptions. Participants were randomly assigned to rate either robot A or robot B to minimise a potential order effect. Robot Mod was only able to act according to its defined patterns, selected from its manufacturing company's website or handcrafted with third-party software.

This could include apologising when a detectable blocking of its users' intended walk path occurred or asking if its work was satisfactory. It was, therefore, able to show human behaviour with no understanding of a situation's general context. On the other hand, Robot Dynamic was capable of seeing different emotions via advanced facial recognition software and linking these to immediate previous events. If a change in mood were linked to its action, robot Dynamic would react accordingly. Even if no such link were found, the interaction would still change depending on its user's mood. It was described to act especially friendly in response to sad emotions or minimise contact while detecting stress. To advance its individualised behaviour, the robot Dynamic collected socioeconomic data about its user, who was also able to complete a personality test on the robot's display to accelerate the process. This personalisation made it possible to link current moods and behaviours to a broader range of possible factors.

Therefore, the robot dynamic could show human behaviour by comprehending the causality of its user's behaviour and concluding mood and motivation. All patterns learned this way, and all collected personal information was explicitly stated to be directly accessible and deletable on the robot itself with no backups. This was included to avoid a rating difference due to loss of control over the machine or the fear of data misuse (Stein et al., 2019). After reading the description, participants were asked to imagine the robot in their household. They were given two minutes to think about possible interactions and everyday life with the specific model to subsequently score their agreement with statements on a 7-point Likert scale concerning the robot's perceived characteristics explained in 'Materials' section. These questionnaires included further items like willingness to buy or use at home to uphold the cover story. Participants repeated this procedure with the other robot's description. All general information was stated to exactly match the ones included in the first description, but participants were asked to reread them to refresh their memories shortly. Following that, they completed the TA, NARS, and IDAQ and nine attention checks to evaluate their responses' conscientiousness. These checks included three general and six model-specific multiple-choice questions with four options. The survey ended with explaining the truly intended research goal and contact details for further questions or complaints.

RESULTS

Pre-registered analysis to test the effect of different mentalisation levels in robots on ascribed attributes while controlling for attitude towards robots, technology commitment, and differences anthropomorphism, we conducted a repeated-measures MANCOVA. The dependent variables, as mentioned in 'Materials' were rated on a seven-point-Likert scale. The Negative Attitudes Towards Robots Scale (Cronbach alpha = .769) and the

Short Scale for technology commitment Individual (Cronbach alpha = .775) were rated on a five-point, while Differences in Anthropomorphism Questionnaire (Cronbach alpha = .825) was rated on a 10-point Likert scale. All of them showed acceptable to good internal consistency and were therefore implemented as covariates. As both stimuli were presented to the participants in a differing order, we also implemented the dummy variable order with 0 for a start with the Mod and 1 for a start with the Dynamic robot as a covariate. The repeated measures MANCOVA shows no significant main effect of the robot model on ascribed attributes in general ($F(1, 215) = .424, p = .515, \text{Wilks}' \Lambda = .998, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .002$) and a strong main effect of the type of attribute ($F(9, 207) = 3.985, p < .05, \text{Wilks}' \Lambda = .852, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .148$). The type of attribute further shows a significant interaction with attitude towards robots ($F(9, 207) = 3.732, p < .05, \text{Wilks}' \Lambda = .860, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .140$) as well as a threefold interaction with order of presentation and model ($F(9, 207) = 9.209, p < .05, \text{Wilks}' \Lambda = .714, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .286$)

Figure 1
 Comparison of Marginal Means Between Two Robots

Note: Evaluation of difference in attributes between models with different order of presentation with non-recoded variables.

Additional analysis

We implemented three more analyses concerning a general attribute variable, attribute-specific effects, and the perceived human-likeness. Given the previously tested interaction effect between attribute and attitude towards robots and order of presentation, we kept these variables as covariates.

Due to a high internal consistency between the attributes (Cronbach alpha = .862-.864), we recoded all negatively phrased items and formed a general attribute variable. A paired sample t-test showed a significantly higher rating for the Mod robot than the Dynamic ($t(219) = -2.907, p = .004$). Moreover the type of model showed a significant effect on the general attribute variable in a repeated measures ANOVA ($F(1, 219) = 8.449, p < .05, \text{Wilks}' \Lambda = .963, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .037$). This effect was stable when controlling for the order of presentation ($F(1, 218) = 8.813, p < .05, \text{Wilks}' \Lambda = .961, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .039$), but lost its significance when controlling for the attitude towards robots ($F(1, 218) = 1.969, p = .165, \text{Wilks}' \Lambda = .991, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .009$). We then replicated Palomäki et al's approach by running individual repeated-measure ANOVAS for all nine attributes of which

three were significant (creepy, scary, and repulsive) to account for the previously found attribute-specificity of effects. After a Bonferroni correction for multiple comparisons only the type of models effect on creepy was still significant ($F(1, 219) = 11.29, p < .05$, Wilks' $\Lambda = .951$, partial $\eta^2 = .049$). Similarly to the analysis of the general attribute variable the effect was stable when controlling for order of presentation ($F(1, 218) = 3.299, p < .05$, Wilks' $\Lambda = .985$, partial $\eta^2 = .048$) but lost its significance when controlling for attitude towards robots ($F(1, 218) = .499, p = .481$, Wilks' $\Lambda = .998$, partial $\eta^2 = .002$). Lastly, we further investigated our third hypothesis about the difference in perceived human likeness between models. A paired sample t-test showed a rating difference between the Mod robot and the Dynamic variant which barely reached significance ($t(219) = -1.979, p = .049$), while the type of model showed a small but significant effect on human-likeness variable in a repeated measures ANOVA ($F(1, 219) = 3.917, p < .05$, Wilks' $\Lambda = .982$, partial $\eta^2 = .018$). The inclusion of presentation order resulted in an increased main effect ($F(1, 218) = 5.522, p < .05$, Wilks' $\Lambda = .975$, partial $\eta^2 = .025$) as well as a strong interaction ($F(1, 218) = 36.231, p < .05$, Wilks' $\Lambda = .857$, partial $\eta^2 = .143$). However controlling for attitude towards robots.

Figure 2
Comparison of Marginal Means Between Two Robots

Note: Evaluation of difference in perceived human-likeness separated by order of presentation

DISCUSSION

Our study presents a derivate of the original uncanny valley theory, and its conclusions have to be treated accordingly. We shifted the focus from a visual to a cognitive level, which most certainly affected certain variables' impact. While the results may drive forward the understanding of the uncanny valley effect, there are some things they cannot accomplish. Firstly, we researched two distinctive expressions of mentalisation, of which we hypothesised to find the largest difference in perception from our participants. The difference found was significant between a non-existent and a very humanlike capability to mentalise. Due to this method, it is impossible to say whether these two are extreme points or how different mentalisation extents compare. We, therefore, cannot add to the debate about the shape of the uncanny valley. Secondly, the study required the participants to imagine an interaction with a robot capable of correlating different events and understanding current emotional and motivational states. While the imaginary exposition can show a potential outcome based on the person's expectations, and in-vivo interaction might have different results. A difference could occur due to additional stimuli or the gap between self-expected and actual behaviour (Epley & Dunning, 2000).

A general problem that has to be faced when defining different degrees of human-likeness in a cognitive setting is conveying information regarding the ability. In our case, this problem concerns the technicality of the given explanation. While it would be easier to compare a robot with human emotions to a model without

affective response mechanisms, the result may lack practicality for realistic machine-human interactions. The imitation of human attributes is ever-evolving and will produce hardly different results from the original mechanism, but the process itself is still different. We approached human-like mentalisation in our robot description with specific functions that produced similar results but were openly explained in their technical nature to account for this difference.

An example would be the detection of emotions via facial recognition software instead of just mentioning the ability to recognise emotions. The technical description offers a feasible link between the robot and the human ability. Possible explanations for the uncanny valley like the category-uncertainty-theory mainly focus on the mismatch between the original object and the added attributes.

A direct opposition between robot and recognises emotion may yield a higher effect than a technical description. Another known problem that gained importance near the end of our study was the order effect. While its original implementation as a covariate was a common choice in conjunction with the repeated-measures design, we did not expect the extent of its influence on the human likeness rating. We found a strong interaction between order and model that led to a more human-like rating for the second robot presented. A possible explanation would be that the participants did not have a prior idea about a normal interaction system. Therefore, the first robot might anchor their expectation of typical robot behaviour, while the second robot could be perceived as more humanlike just by differing from the established norm. While we found a significant difference in favour of our hypothesis, human-likeness might not just be a given property. This could be relevant for the uncanny valley effect when considering that a morphed image approach, a series of pictures that show the gradual morph from a non-human to a human face, is often used to test it. This method presupposes that the images are more humanlike with an increasing portion of the human image.

Considering the significant interaction between order and human likeness, this might not be the case. The series often starts with the pure non-human image, which gives an anchor for the following pictures and, in turn, more human. If the participants were presented with the images in a different or random order, the *uncanniest* picture might not be considered very humanlike. A morphed-image approach is random order, or the usage of pretested but unrelated images might be a more valid way to link human-likeness and uncanniness. The 'uncanniness' we could discover was limited to the significantly creepier perception of the dynamic robot. While the original study proposing the nine-item-composition for uncanniness (Palomäki et al., 2018) also only found significant differences for some of them, one relevant difference could be considered a vague indication at best. Sadly, uncanniness is not strictly defined in most studies, and even the original proposal describes this aspect rather abstract as eerie' (Mori, 1970, as cited in MacDorman & Kageki, 2012, p.99).

Our sample showed high reliability and, in our opinion, good content validity of Palomäki et al.'s scale (2018), which is why we would encourage its usage as an uncanny measurement in further studies. We, therefore, stick to what our data can support. The difference found between the robots can be interpreted in favour of a 'creepy' valley that concerns mentalisation. It is a topic that future developments in robotic should take into consideration while marketing similar dynamic interaction systems. The methods of avoiding a cognitive uncanny valley effect might differ from their visual counterpart. Throughout the study, the NARS proved to be a covariate that nullified some significant differences in rating when being accounted for. With items like 'If robots had emotions, I would be willing to befriend them.' (Syrdal et al., 2009), overlap with the reception of mentalisation capabilities was foreseeable, but the extent was surprising to us.

The NARS was implemented to capture the salient and verbalisable opinions about robots that may have formed based on individual experiences or medial influences. While the different explanations for the uncanny valley vary in their main emphasis, they describe it as a reaction stemming from deeply rooted mechanisms. For the perception of mentalisation this does not seem to be the case. The exclusion of the salient opinion did not lead to a significant instinctual effect, which influenced the robot's rating beyond declarable reason. We cannot say whether this is a definitive difference between the visual and cognitive uncanniness as we did not find studies concerning the visual aspect which implemented a comparable covariate. However, many other covariates and their effect on the uncanny valley's sensitivity are researched (MacDorman & Entezari, 2015). For robotics, this finding might imply that potential adverse reactions to human-like intelligent systems can be avoided by evoking a positive attitude towards robots from the recipient. As for the difference between the uncanny valley based on visual or cognitive attributes, we already mentioned our study to be a derivative of the theory, making it harder to draw direct conclusions and explore and understand the uncanny valley phenomenon. Some of the uncanny valley's theoretical explanations could also explain the cognitive variant, while other approaches are more difficult to apply. For example, it is feasible that recognising human cognition in a biologically lifeless shell might remind us of our mortality just as much as a stiff or irregular facial expression (Tinwell et al., 2011).

The category-uncertainty theory presents a similarly applicable solution for the unease of mismatching cognitive abilities and visuals. To explain both phenomena with the avoidance of pathogens, however, is far more complex. These hints can be considered when deciding which theory explains the uncanny valley to the furthest degree but depends on the relation of the two effects. Future studies should therefore investigate the relationship between visual and cognitive aspects that create an uncanny effect. Related topics would be the ascription of mental capabilities due to physical traits (Talamas et al., 2016), possible interactions between both effects, and the extent to which these effects could be considered the same phenomenon. A starting point could also be to investigate whether the individual attitude towards robots affects the visual uncanny valley similarly.

Another important piece of information for robotics would be the optimal technical description to involve when explaining or marketing a robot's cognitive features. Our data showed the individual attitude towards robots to be the main contributor to ascribing attributes. Therefore, it should be further explored which factors mainly influence it, how stable or changeable it is, and which methods could be deployed to avoid an uncanny perception by recipients. In light of these results, robots could be considered a particular case with a time limit when researching the effect of cognitive similarities to humans. A puppet is neither expected to understand emotions nor asked for the display of complicated mental processes.

On the other hand, robots are heading towards new stages of independent functionality and tend to resemble their creators more with every achieved step. While we were able to show that a process imitating human mentalisation leads to a creepier perception of the robot, future generations might be much less irritated by this concept. With the evolution of robots and their integration into everyday life, a thinking and feeling tin man might be another daily occurrence.

CONCLUSION

Our main hypotheses expected the ability of mentalisation in robots to affect the ascribed attributes uniformly. Although we found an overall effect implying the more positive perception of the robot model without mentalisation capability, the specific attribute differences varied greatly. The only significant effect on the attribute level after implementing the Bonferroni correction was creepy. While a robot with a cognitive ability often assessed to be human-specific is perceived as creepier than a model that only performs predefined behavioural patterns, falls in line with the assumptions of the uncanny valley, it does not confirm the extent of our assumptions. Both the general and the specific effect became non-significant when controlling for the participants' attitude towards robots. The implication of this covariate will be further discussed, but it has to be stated that we did not anticipate its impact on the results. Individual differences in anthropomorphism and technology commitment showed minor effects on the outcome but were not nearly as detrimental to the significance of the results. Our main hypotheses: (1) Robots with the ascribed ability of mentalisation will be rated significantly lower in positive attributes than robots lacking this ability; and (2) Robots with the ascribed ability of mentalisation will be rated significantly higher in negative attributes than robots lacking this ability. Therefore, it cannot be sufficiently supported and have to be falsified. Our secondary hypothesis expected that mentalisation in robots would humanize them in our participants' eyes and result in a higher human-likeness ascription than for the normal variant.

We found a small but significant effect in favour of our hypothesis. The main effect, however, grows when accounting for the order of presentation. A significant interaction between the robot model and order implies a tendency to rate the second robot as more humanlike regardless of its features. While this effect certainly has to be considered when interpreting the results, they showed an overall higher human-likeness rating for the dynamic robot. Our secondary hypothesis: (3) Robots with the ascribed ability of mentalisation will be rated significantly more humanlike than robots lacking this ability. Therefore, it can be verified. The effect, however, is also strongly susceptible to the exclusion of attitude towards robots. Overall, our study showed a strong influence of conscious and declarable opinions on the extent of ascribing specific attributes to robots.

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